

THE INFLUENCE OF CULTURAL VALUES ON THE MEDIA COVERAGE OF FEMALES IN BOKO HARAM TERRORISM IN NIGERIA

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Abstract: *Boko Haram terrorism in Borno State North-East Nigeria between 2009 and 2019 was women-centric as the sect engaged them as kinetic and non-kinetic tactical tools. Females were used as suicide bombers, recruiters and procreators of future Boko Haram jihadists. While some women and girls willingly joined the group, and made themselves willing tools, a vast majority were coerced into becoming tactical tools, thus, they evolved from victimhood to become perpetrators. The use of females as tactical tools in the terrorism sent shockwaves across the globe, attracting global news coverage, especially from the electronic media. However, the news coverage of these women by broadcasters were skewed in part due to factors premised on cultural values. patriarchal cultural values influenced the women's willingness to share their lived experiences with the media. They also impacted the worldviews of frontline journalists who covered the armed conflicts thereby influenced the types of events that were considered news worthy. In news reports, frontline journalists inferred that women were passive participants of the terrorism, failing to recognise their roles as perpetrators and conspirators. Using the history method, qualitative data were gathered from primary and secondary sources. Oral interviews from frontline journalists who reported the terrorism for the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), the Cable News Network (CNN), Al Jazeera, Nigeria Television Authority (NTA) and Channels Television; military personnel, aid workers, Boko Haram commanders, wives of Boko Haram members were analysed, to determine how cultural values impacted news coverage. This paper posited that patriarchal cultural values fostered unconscious biases in the journalists who covered the conflicts. and that through their coverage they exonerated women from taking responsibilities for their violent extremist behaviours.*

Introduction

Feminisation of its violent conflicts was a distinct feature of Boko Haram terrorism in Borno State,

North-East Nigeria. Boko Haram abducted large numbers of women and girls and used them as tactical tools. The jihadist sect used women as

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suicide bombers, recruiters, slaves and for the procreation of its own kind. Different categories of women lived within the Boko Haram organisation. While the most prominent category were the coerced women or the victims, the sect had among them women who were sympathetic to the course and women who were militarised and perpetrated heinous acts within Boko Haram territories or *Daulla*.¹ It also had in its ranks female victims who turned perpetrators or sympathisers in the course of living with their husbands in the *Daulla*.² Despite the existence of these other groups of women, the gendered or women centric nature of the terrorism went largely unnoticed by the electronic media until the abduction of the Chibok school girls' in April 2014. The Chibok school girls abduction drew the attention of the international media to a terrorist organisation which hitherto was considered local. Subsequently, the conflict gained substantive coverage in the electronic media.

Still, these women remained underrepresented. On the few occasions when they made it to the news, they were featured either as suicide bombers or as victims of the conflicts. Female perpetrators and sympathisers slipped under the radar of journalists due to the influence of cultural values. These cultural influences impacted the women and journalists alike.

Scholarly works with diverse thematic concerns existed on the women in the Boko Haram terrorism, the intersections of identity, and how the print media covered them. Much of these literature centred their examination on just one group of females, the victims of the terrorism. Thus, they overlooked the other roles they played as perpetrators and conspirators. Also, very limited literature had interrogated the electronic media's coverage of women in the conflicts. It is this lacuna that this study attempted to fill. It interrogated the factors behind the limited coverage of women by five electronic media outfits: the British Broadcasting Corporation (BBC), the Cable News Network (CNN), Al Jazeera, Nigeria Television Authority (NTA) and Channels Television. This work employed the history method of qualitative research design and methodology. Using these, it gathered and analysed primary and secondary data through relevant literature, and oral interviews with journalists from the five media organisations, Nigeria army personnels, and aid workers who served within the Boko Haram theatre of conflicts, and repentant male and female Boko Haram combatants. It argued that certain cultural values were inhibitors that led to the underrepresentation of women. To formulate the issue at hand, the following questions were

¹ Interview with Fatima Akilu, 59, Director for Behavioural Analysis and Strategy at the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA), provided a national security corridor for the disengagement of Boko Haram militants, Abuja, 10-08-23.

² Interview with Lilian Ngosu Unaegbu, 42, gender and communications expert in Peace and Conflict who transverses the NGO sector: Oxfam, UNSAID and UN Women, Abuja, 03-10-23.

interrogated: how did cultural values influence the women living within Boko Haram's theatre of conflicts? In what ways did cultural prejudices impact editorial judgement of journalists as they covered the conflicts? and, how did an intersection of findings from questions one and two led to the invincibility of female perpetrators in the terrorism?

Conceptualising Terrorism, Cultural Values and Coverage Of Women

The concepts of terrorism, cultural values, and coverage of women were three terms relevant to this paper. Thus, they were clarified and contextualised for the purpose of this study.

Terrorism

Scholars of conflict and security studies contested whether Boko Haram was an insurgency or a terrorism. This was in part due to the overlapping characteristics of the concept of insurgency and terrorism, and also due to the nature of the sect's evolution over time. Thus, It is imperative to have a proper understanding and an in-depth analysis of the facts in a given political violence to determine its form.³

Conceptualisation of insurgency and terrorism had yielded no results as there was a lack of "common understanding and perception of ethics, history [and] politics."⁴ A juxtaposition of both terms in relation to Boko Haram is imperative to determine the most suitable concept for this study.

Insurgency is a revolt against a political system using "violent methods to resist the enforcement of law."⁵ The aim is to force fundamental change in the "political and economic status quo."⁶ Indeed, insurgency is agitation for political and economic changes using terrorism. It controls territories where it exerts its political ideology and aims to achieve its goals. On the other hand, terrorism is the systematic use of coercion, violence and destructive acts to intimidate constituted government, a population or individuals. it sways public opinions through "bloodletting," "primitive deception and stealth."⁷ Terrorism targets mostly civilian or non-combatants members of the military force, and the number of perpetrators are predominantly smaller in size.⁸ They are

³ NATO, "Counterinsurgency: A Generic Reference Curriculum," NATO and OTAN, (2017), 3. accessed 13 February 2023.

https://www.nato.int/nato_static_fl2014/assets/pdf/pdf_2017_09/20170904_1709-counterinsurgency-rc.pdf

⁴ Mustafa C. Ünal, "Terrorism versus Insurgency: A conceptual analysis," *Crime, Law and Social Change* 66, no.1 (January 2016): 21-25. DOI: 10.1007/s10611-015-9601-7.

⁵ Ahmed O. Adam, "Boko Haram Since 2009: A Study in Security History," 7th Professorial Inaugural Lecture Series,

Nigerian Defence Academy, (n.d.), 30. <https://www.academia.edu/37604598/>.

⁶ Steven Metz, *The Future of Insurgency*, (Pennsylvania: USAWC Press, 1993), 15.

⁷ Ahmed O. Adam, "Boko Haram Since 2009: A Study in Security History," 35.

⁸ Assaf Moghadam, "The interplay between terrorism, insurgency, and civil war in the Middle East," *Analyses of the Elcano Royal Institute* 4, no. 8. (January 2015): 2-3.

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uncompromisingly violent, do not hold territories, and do not function as an open arms unit.⁹ Insurgents exhibit the traits of terrorists through its violent methods of bloodletting. Still, while insurgency employ acts of terrorism to achieve its goals, and therefore insurgents are terrorists, the reverse cannot be said that terrorists are insurgents.

Taking cognisance of the dynamics of both concepts therefore, it could be argued that under Abubakar Shekau's leadership between 2010 and 2015, the sect exhibited the traits of an insurgency.¹⁰ It improved its military capabilities, employed more brutal tactics and strategies, advanced its political ideology and controlled a territory the size of Belgium which it ran as a shadow state.¹¹ However, over the years the Nigeria military recaptured those territories and sacked the group, sending them deep in to the forests. Ever since, Boko Haram had operated as a terrorist organisation and not an insurgent organisation.

Cultural Values

⁹ Moghadam, "The interplay between terrorism, insurgency, and civil war in the Middle East," 6.

¹⁰ James A. Falode, "The Nature of Nigeria's Boko Haram War 2010-2015: A Strategic Analysis," *Perspectives on Terrorism* 10, no. 1, (February 2016): 43- 44.

¹¹ Reliefweb, "Nigeria: Persistent Boko Haram threat (24 December 2015)," reliefweb.int. Published 24 December 2015. <https://reliefweb.int/map/nigeria/nigeria-persistent-boko-haram-threat-24-dec-2015>.

It would be impossible to draw a conceptual clarification on cultural values without first examining religion and culture, the bedrocks of these values. Religion is any set of beliefs or practices that involves the supernatural.¹² It is a "system of symbols" that formulate the conceptions or ideas of a general order of existence clothed in an aura of factuality that seem "uniquely realistic."¹³ These systems of symbols include designated behaviours and worldviews. Culture is the complex whole that includes "knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom, and any other capabilities and habits" that a human acquires as part of society.

Religion and culture are distinct, yet interrelated. Religion influences culture and culture determines religion.¹⁴ They both forge designated behaviours, moral norms and mores, that sum up the cultural values of a society. These cultural values determined the basic underlying assumptions which exist at the subconscious level. They are the main determiners behind how people in each society "perceive, think and feel."¹⁵ People interpret and make sense of events

¹² Max F. Müller, *Lectures on the Science of Language* 5th Edition 15, (Westminister: Royal Institute of Great Britain, 1965) 399.

¹³ Clifford Geertz, *The Interpretation of Cultures*, 90, (New York: Basic Books, Inc., 1973).

¹⁴ Jaco Beyers, "Religion and culture: Revisiting a close relative," *HTS Theological Studies* 73, no. 1, (2017): 2. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v73i1.3864>.

¹⁵ Helen Spencer-Oatey, "What is culture? A compilation of quotations," *GlobalPAD Core Concepts*, (2012). DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29603.37925.

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as they occur in their daily lives through frames or schema of interpretations¹⁶ derived from cultural values. These schema of interpretations as determined by cultural values enables them "locate, perceive, identify and label a seemingly infinite number of concrete occurrences."¹⁷ It was within this context that this study referred to cultural values

Coverage of Women

Electronic media's underrepresentation of women in conflict zones had in recent decades been a talking point for academics in the fields of peace, conflicts and gender studies. Women were rarely featured in news, and matters related to them less equitably covered. While Men were featured as analyst, perpetrators and source of solutions, women hardly "featured in the analysis of conflicts," their perspectives and the complex roles they played went unrecognised.¹⁸ Opinions of females were rarely sort after. When they made the news, they were featured primarily "from the perspective of victims"¹⁹ or instruments of war such as female suicide bombers. Female perpetrators, conspirators and

sympathisers were downplayed. Thus, coverage were often skewed and mostly unsustainable.

The concept of women coverage promoted more accurate portrayal of the lived experiences of women and girls on the mainstream media. This is considered imperative since the media has the power to shape social conversations and influence public perceptions. It shapes public perceptions about women and men, and for this reason it is essential that it "shuns stereotypes that limit and trivialise women."²⁰ In this way it can accurately portray their world. For the purpose of this paper, coverage of women referred to the ways in which women in the Boko Haram organisation were featured in the news and how this shaped the public perceptions of women.

Influence of Cultural Values on Females and Journalists in the Boko Haram Conflicts

Social constructs and worldviews drawn from cultural values are embodied in patriarchy. Islam, like other dominant religions in the globe, is a custodian of patriarchy. It ascribes socially defined roles that are set distinctly for the male

¹⁶ Gregory Bateson, *Steps to an Ecology of Mind: Collected Essays in Anthropology, Psychology, Evolution and Epistemology*, 7, (San Francisco, CA: Chandler, 1972).

¹⁷ Erving Goffman, *Frame Analysis: An Eassy on the Organisation of Experience*, 21, (Cambridge: Havard University Press, 1974).

¹⁸ African Union and UN Women, *Handbook for Reporters on Women, Peace and Security: Practicing Gender-Responsive*

Reporting In Conflict Affected Countries In Africa, 2, (Addis Ababa, Africa Union Commission, 2017).

¹⁹ UN Women, *Guidelines for Gender and Conflict-sensitive Reporting*, 9, (Geneva: UN Women, 2019).

²⁰ UN Women, *Guidelines for Gender and Conflict-sensitive Reporting*, 9.

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gender and the female gender.²¹ Islam is a conservative religion which had been practiced in the North-East of Nigeria since the 11th centuries,²² and had a fundamental influence on the people. In addition to this was Boko Haram's terrorist campaigns between 2009 and 2019, which was based on an ideology that favoured the traditional Salafi movement.²³ This further enforced extremist practices on the society. A cursory look at this patriarchal Muslim society, revealed that social and religious practices determined how women conducted and expressed themselves in public spaces. Women were expected to stay out of public discussions, not express personal opinions and not to have agency.

Also, journalists as products of these cultural orientations were not immune to its influences. They were confronted with biases that limited their output on women involvement in the violent conflicts during coverage. It was within these stringent religious and cultural frames that this study drew accounts of military personnel, government officials, aid workers and journalists who extensively covered the violent conflicts,

boots-on-ground between 2009 and 2019. These accounts were contextualised into the following categories: Literacy deficiency due to cultural inhibitions; women portrayed as weak and lacking agency; socio-cultural sensitivities; patriarchal restrictions on access to women; unconscious biases as media promote stereotypes.

Literacy Deficiency Due to Cultural Inhibitions

Cultural values largely determined the worth attached to literacy in the North-East region of the country. Literacy goes beyond the ability to read and write to include cognitive skills, capacity building and the acquisition of tools for critical reflection. This region suffered a low literacy level.²⁴ Although parents and guardians enrolled their children and wards in Islamic education alongside western education, in more conservative Muslim communities parents tended to opt exclusively for Qur'anic education as against formal education.²⁵ This deficiency in formal education posed a challenge for journalists who had to work with the illiterate population. Juxtaposing her cultural orientation

²¹ Mohammed A. Ali, "Key Concepts in Gender Studies: Patriarchy and Religion," (MA Gender Studies 1st Semester, Jamia Millia Islamia University, n.d.). <https://www.academia.edu/45530613/>.

²² University of Leiden. "Islam in Nigeria." Published n.d. <https://www.ascleiden.nl/content/webdossiers/islam-nigeria>.

²³ Alexander Thurston, "Boko Haram from Salafism to Jihadism," *Boko Haram and the Canon Part III*, (2016): 195-197. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9781316661987.009>.

²⁴ Emmanuel A. Isah, Suleman Yakubu, and Timothy T. Adeleke, "Socio-Cultural Factors and Access To University Education in North-East Region of Nigeria" *East African Journal of Educational Research and Policy* 15, no. 1, (June 2020): 60-61.

²⁵ E Isah, Yakubu, and Adeleke, "Socio-Cultural Factors and Access To University Education... 3.

as a French woman empowered to express opinions on issues pertaining her existence, with her experience on the fields, freelance journalist, Benedict Kurzen,²⁶ posited that, speaking to people who lacked capacity for self-expression was a challenge she had to deal with.²⁷ A lack of self-expression in part made women shy away from the media, and when they were willing to speak, articulation of thoughts and ideas became a challenge.

Women Portrayed as Weak and Lacking Agency

Stipulated gender roles required women to be protective homemakers and an epitome of life, gentle, nurturing, just because they were biologically females. This social construct skewed the news coverage of Boko Haram violence which projected women as passive participants in the terrorism and as lacking agency. Data gathered from the study revealed that, majority of the interviewees keyed into these pre-existing stereotypes. Through this lens, females in Boko Haram were projected as frail and vulnerable victims of the terrorism. An aid worker interviewed for this study affirmed that only women victims lived within the sect. “I did

not see any woman that is a perpetrator, all of them were victims of Boko Haram.”²⁸ In tandem, General Sarkin Yaki Bello²⁹ retired, explained that, as wives, daughters and mothers of terrorists, these women were placed in a subservient position without capacity to execute agency. Hence, violent extremism perpetrated by women in Boko Haram were attributed to coercion.

It is imperative to state at this point that this paper in no way inferred that all women who perpetrated violent acts or who conspired in the execution of violent acts had agency. Rather, it posited that while women were genuinely coerced into anti-social activities by the terrorists, there were also in existence women who exercised agency, committed heinous crimes in the name of the terrorist organisation, but were lumped in with victims and shielded from facing the consequences for their actions.

Fatima Akilu,³⁰ the pioneer coordinator of the deradicalisation and reintegration programme for repentant Boko Haram terrorists, organised by Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA) in 2015, argued that in spite of stereotype belief that women were solely victims

²⁶ Interview with Benedict Kruzen, 44, Freelance journalist based in Maiduguri in the first decade of the conflicts; reported and provided support for diverse international media organisations, including the BBC, phone interview, 22-04-23.

²⁷ Interview with Benedict Kruzen, 44,...

²⁸ Interview with Auwal Ibrahim Musa, 55, Head of Transparency International (Nigeria), Amnesty International (Nigeria) Board of Trustee Chairman, Abuja, 10-08-23.

²⁹ Interview with Sarkin Yaki Bello, 67, Major General rtd. First coordinator Nigeria Counterinsurgency and Counterterrorism in the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA) from 2011-2014, Abuja, 10-08-23.

³⁰ Interview with Fatima Akilu, 59,...

in the conflicts, in reality there were women perpetrators.³¹ One fundamental reason why this fact was overlooked she opined was that: “Culturally we want to believe that women are always passive participants or victims of conflicts, but the realities are different.”³² According to Akilu, during one of her deradicalisation sessions, a Boko Haram commander’s wife boasted about how she killed her father’s friend and how she had planned to kill her father for failing to pay her a condolence visit after the death of her commander husband. These sorts of confessions were not uncommon amongst female members of the jihadist sect, whom from Akilu’s psychological analysis at the time, did not seem to act under coercion but rather exercised agency. Yet the Nigerian government freed these women without consequences for their actions, some of them were reintegrated back into society; and the journalists failed to hold these perpetrators to account in their coverage. One reason for this failure, according to one of the journalists interviewed, was the editorial policy which required they carried out duty-of-care on the women whom they considered vulnerable. Therefore, he opined “you don’t show a woman who is alleged to have been involved in terrorism,” as this further made her vulnerable.³³

This blanket grouping was reflective of the influence of religion and culture on how these personae interpreted what happened to the women around them. The likelihood that women had ability to execute agency while exhibiting violent extremist behaviours was not an intentional consideration.

Socio-Cultural Sensitivities

Rape, sexual slavery, and forced marriages left women caught in the terrorism vulnerable. However, it was a challenge getting them to share these lived experiences due to socio-cultural sensitivities,. Topics that bordered on sex, rape and sexual exploitations were flocked with dire consequences. This cultural conundrum posed a challenge to journalists, who observed that “anything sex is a taboo.”³⁴ And “taboos” of these sorts meant discussions that involved words like ‘sex’ and ‘rape’ were herculean. This presented legitimate concerns on how cultural values influenced the attitudes of the women whose stories needed to be told.

Beyond the outcome of illiteracy and the limitations imposed on the use of taboo words, was the culture of silence derived from social sensitivities wherein the society enforced an unwritten code of ‘not washing dirty linens in public.’ This unwritten code compelled women into silence. As one BBC reporter described it,

³¹ Interview with Fatima Akilu, 59,...

³² Interview with Fatima Akilu, 59,...

³³ Interview with Emperor Simon, 39, Channels Television reporter, covered the Boko Haram conflicts for six years, Abuja, 22-01-23.

³⁴ Interview with Benedict Kruzen, 44,...

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the Muslim women had “a tradition of keeping silent even when they are dying, unless they have the permission from their husbands or male folks to speak due to religious restraints.”³⁵

Patriarchal restrictions on access to women

Access to female sources by male journalists, were in certain cases restricted by traditional rulers, husbands and brothers. In highly conservative Muslim communities, male journalists had on some occasions met with hostilities as they tried to access women sources. Recounting his experience, Emperor Simon, a reporter with Channels Television, opined that when approached for stories, women sources would sometimes “tell you they need to seek the consent of their husbands. Sometimes the men can turn violent and tell you they will not allow their women to talk.”³⁶ Same were the cases in the IDP camps, where even widowed women needed the permission of camp leaders who were men, to speak with men journalists. The reason for this according to Simon, is “because in some of those camps the men were the ones in charge. You have to get clearance from the men. They are the ones to find you another women to serve as a go-between” you and your female source.”³⁷ This reflected the conservative cultural and religious practices that guided permissible interactions

between women and the men not related to them. For these male journalists, breakthroughs to female sources entailed crossing hurdles to get willing sources. In his experience getting female sources for his stories, one journalist asserted that, he often got women who were willing to speak with him, but “I knew what I had to do underground” to make this happen.³⁸ Deals occurred ‘underground.’ Often times male relatives were paid by journalists before they granted permission for the women to be interviewed. Other times aid workers stood as obstacles in reaching these women, and journalists made compromises which included tailoring the news stories to suit obvious NGO biases, but this is outside the scope of this paper. Conversely, female journalists appeared to have enjoyed easier access to women and security sources. They had access into the homes of their female sources, and they conducted interviews with the women unsupervised. In this way, women gave more candid information to the journalists about their experiences. It also seemed that being female provided more favourable access to security sources. Female journalists attested that security agents were more opened and more understanding and even

³⁵ Interview with Chris Ewokor, 52, BBC World Service senior reporter for Africa, Abuja, 15-01-23.

³⁶ Interview with Emperor Simon, 39,...

³⁷ Interview with Emperor Simon, 39,...

³⁸ Interview with Bitrus Dogara, Channels Television reporter based in Maiduguri, reporting the conflicts in the North-East since 2015, Maiduguri, 01-02-23.

sometimes concerned about their safety.³⁹ While this might be perceived as positive, it was in fact counterproductive. It implied that a shortage of women journalists meant limited access to the women and girls within Boko Haram's territories.

Unconscious Biases as Media Promote Stereotypes

Generic human factors or unconscious biases derived from socialisation and life experiences, reflected in some of the ways journalists covered the Boko Haram violent extremism. Self-censorship was not uncommon. There were instances wherein certain incidents occurred but were ignored by journalists because reporting them were either not in their personal interest or that of their media houses.⁴⁰ In other instances events were couched in words that projected stereotypes and hate. Also, the Nigeria media was sectionalised, regionalised and religionised with biases which bordered on ethnic and religious lines. These reflected in the choice of words journalists used in their reportage. And in some instances, such language exposed the females to sexual predators.⁴¹ Put differently, these biases often manifest in the news frames chosen by journalists to report events and in the choice of words used in their narrations. This in

turn projected stereotypes, hate and other forms of unconscious biases.

For the most part of the conflicts between 2009 and 2019, international media organisations including the CNN and Al Jazeera engaged non-Nigerian journalists in the coverage of the Boko Haram terrorism. Of course, whether this was an error of omission or commission is subject to further studies by scholars. Nonetheless, findings revealed that this seemed to be the case, based on accounts by foreign journalists who testified that, since they were on the frontlines, they often provided support for international journalists not based in Nigeria. It was inferred that a major factor for this was to avoid inherent biases from local journalists.⁴²

Indeed, it can be argued that certain benefits were accrued to foreign journalists who covered the crises. Numerous accounts affirmed that victims of the conflicts willingly open up to foreign journalists. One presumption alluded to the fact that victims considered these journalists as outsiders to their culture, society and everything they knew. Therefore these journalists provided safe spaces for them to reveal secrets and lived experiences that they ordinarily would not share with local journalists. Kurzen affirmed: "Sometimes when you are facing journalists of photographers who are

³⁹ Interview with Yvonne Ndege, 45, correspondent for the Al Jazeera news network, spent very long stints in Maiduguri reporting events of the conflicts since 2009, phone interview, 19-01-23.

⁴⁰ Interview with Yvonne Ndege, 45,...

⁴¹ Interview with Emperor Simon, 39,...

⁴² Interview with Yvonne Ndege, 45,...

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coming from the same cultural background, maybe you will be scared to disclose somethings.”⁴³ However, this is not to say that local journalists did not get breakthroughs to female victims who found them trustworthy enough to share their experiences in spite of the trust deficits.

Conclusion

Cultural values in North-East of Nigeria posed challenges to the coverage of Boko Haram terrorism. Challenges such as information blockade due to patriarchal restrictions and socio-cultural sensitivities, the presupposition that women were weak and lacked agency, and the unconscious bias as the media promoted stereotypes, hindered objective reporting of the violent extremism. An analysis of primary and secondary data revealed that worldviews derived from cultural values deeply imprinted on members of the society, operatives of the Nigeria Army, aid workers and journalists, all of whom were actors in the media coverage of the violent extremism. These imprinted social constructs, were expressed, not just by the society’s attitude towards women, but also on frontline journalists preexisting opinions, worldviews, ideologies, impressions and perceptions. Caught in the web of social expectations forged from stipulated social norms, journalists failed to be responsive to the women-centric nature of the terrorism due to lack of skills. Stereotype narrative promoted

by the media limited the knowledge available of the actual roles the females played in the sect. Therefore, the numerous factors highlighted in this paper brought to the fore the need for further studies on the divergent ways cultural values influence news coverage of the Boko Haram terrorism. Also, an in-depth examination of women’s roles in Boko Haram violent extremism beyond being victims, is required for in-depth understanding of this integral, yet overlooked aspect of the terrorism. To achieve these, trainings on gender is imperative for frontline counterterrorism personnels such as the military, aid workers and journalists to enable them see women combatants beyond socially designated behavioural patterns.

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⁴³ Interview with Benedict Kruzen, 44,...

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Table 1: List of contributors in oral interviews

S/N	Name of contributors	Age	Title/Occupation	Place of interview	Date
1	Auwal Ibrahim Musa	55	Head of Transparency International (Nigeria), Amnesty International (Nigeria) Board of Trustee Chairman	Abuja	10-08-23
2	Benedict Kruzen	44	Freelance journalist based in Maiduguri in the first decade of the conflicts; reported and provided support for diverse international media organisations, including the BBC	phone interview	22-04-23
3	Bitrus Dogara	37	Channels Television reporter based in Maiduguri, reporting the conflicts in the North-East since 2015	Maiduguri	01-02-23
4	Chris Ewokor	52	BBC World Service senior reporter for Africa	Abuja	15-01-23
5	Emperor Simon	39	Channels Television reporter, covered the Boko Haram conflicts for six years,	Abuja	22-01-23
6	Fatima Akilu	59	Director for Behavioural Analysis and Strategy at the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA), provided a national security	Abuja	10- 08- 23

Onyinye Chime

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			corridor for the disengagement of Boko Haram militants		
7	Lilian Ngosu Unaegbu	42	Gender and communications expert in Peace and Conflict who transversed the NGO sector: Oxfam, UNSAID and UN Women	Abuja	03-10-23
8	Sarkin Yaki Bello	67	Major General rtd. First coordinator Nigeria Counterinsurgency and Counterterrorism in the Office of the National Security Adviser (ONSA) from 2011-2014	Abuja	10-08-23
9	Yvonne Ndege	45	Correspondent for the Al Jazeera news network, spent very long stints in Maiduguri reporting events of the conflicts since 2009	phone interview	19-01-23

Onyinye Chime